

Studies in Condensed Phosphates: Part XIV. Cesium Polymetaphosphate and its Complex Derivatives with Calcium, Zinc, Nickel and Magnesium

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Cesium polymetaphosphate and a number of its complex derivatives with the composition $(\text{Cs}_{2/3}\text{M}_{1/6}\text{PO}_3)_n$ (where M=Ca, Zn, Mg and Ni) have been synthesised by fusion technique. The conductance measurements at different formal concentrations show a greater resemblance to Graham's salt, lithium polymetaphosphate and their complex derivatives. Measurements of molecular weights by end-group titration method indicate their polymeric character.

The polymetaphosphates have acquired a very interesting position in the field of inorganic polymers. The sodium and potassium polymetaphosphates have been studied extensively and a number of reviews¹⁻⁶ have appeared in the literature. The polymeric nature of these compounds is now well established being supported by many important studies like viscosity, light-scattering, sedimentation studies etc. by a number of workers^{7,8} of the field.

Although it was E. Vonberg⁹ who first of all obtained cesium polymetaphosphate in the beginning of this century, a survey of the literature reveals that very little work has been done on the study of this polymetaphosphate. Osterheld and Markowitz¹⁰ studied the dehydration of cesium dihydrogen orthophosphate by thermal analysis, X-ray and weight loss data and concluded that the following reaction was taking place:

But simple dehydration of the mono-alkali dihydrogen phosphate in the absence of condensation, produces trimetaphosphate¹¹

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2. B., Topley, *Quart. Rev.*, 1949, **3**, 345.
3. J. R. Van Wazer, C. F. Callis and P. C. Arvan, *Chem. Rev.*, 1954, **54**, 777.
4. E. Thilo, *Advances in Inorganic and Radiochemistry*, Vol. IV by H. J. Emeleus and A. G. Sharpe., Academic Press Inc., New York, 1962, I.
5. R. E. Hall, U. S. Patent 1,956, 515, 24 April 1934.
6. J. R. Van Wazer and C. F. Callis, *Chem. Rev.*, 1958 **58**, 1011.
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9. E. Von Berg., *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 4182.
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In these laboratories¹²⁻¹⁶, complex derivatives of Graham's salt, Kurrol's potassium salt and of lithium polymetaphosphate have been prepared by heating the corresponding alkali metal dihydrogen phosphate (or alkali metal carbonate + ammonium dihydrogen phosphate in the case of lithium) bivalent metal oxide or carbonate, and diammonium hydrogen orthophosphate in the requisite mole ratios. Complex derivatives of the type $(M_x^I M^{II}_{1-x} PO_3)_n$ (where $M^I = Na, K$ or Li , $M^{II} = Ca, Ba, Sr, Zn, Cd, Pb, Cu, Ni, Mg$

or Be , $x = 2/3, 1/2$ or $1/3$ and a is valency of the metal atom M^{II}) have been obtained. The reaction may be represented as :

All these derivatives have been extensively studied and it is concluded that these are all polymeric long chain compounds. The properties are similar to that of Graham's salt and the conductance studies etc. depict their polyelectrolytic nature. As already pointed out that cesium polymetaphosphate appears to have been less studied, hence it was considered worthwhile to prepare complex cesium polyemetaphosphate derivatives with bivalent metals and to study their polymeric character.

The present communication deals with the synthesis of cesium polymetaphosphate and its complex derivatives of the type $[Cs_4 M (PO_3)_6]_n$ where $M = Ca, Zn, Mg$ and Ni . The conductance studies of these derivatives have been made and their molecular weights have been determined by endgroup titration methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus and Materials : All the reagents used were of chemically pure grade. A Gallenkamp muffle furnace with thermostatic control of $\pm 25^\circ$ was used for preparing the samples. All the measurements were made after 24 hrs of dissolution of the compound so as to attain equilibrium³. The details for the conductometric and the pH metric studies are the same as already described¹⁵.

Preparation of the samples : Cesium polymetaphosphate and its complex derivatives were prepared by fusion reactions of the following type :

where $M = Ca, Zn, Mg$ and Ni .

12. R. C. Mehrotra and V. S. Gupta., *Jour. Polymer Sci.*, 1961, **54**, 613-620.
13. R. C. Mehrotra and V. S. Gupta, *Kolloid Z. fur Polymere* (1960), **184**, 1, 30-36.
14. R. C. Mehrotra and P. C. Vyas, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1965, **A3**, 2535.
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In the case of nickel, the carbonate salt was used instead of the oxide. In almost all the cases a clear melt was obtained which gave a clear glass on chilling between cold stainless steel plates except in the case of cesium polymetaphosphate where an opaque glass, like that of Kurrol's potassium salt was obtained. All these derivatives were easily soluble in water.

TABLE I

Analysis of complex cesium polymetaphosphate derivatives $[\text{Cs}_4\text{M}(\text{PO}_3)_6]_n$

Compound	Cesium		Metal		Phosphorous	
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
$(\text{CsPO}_3)_n$	61.25	62.72	—	—	14.68	14.62
$(\text{Cs}_{2/3}\text{Ca}_{1/6}\text{PO}_3)_n$	50.00	50.84	3.94	3.83	17.84	17.78
$(\text{Cs}_{2/3}\text{Mg}_{1/6}\text{PO}_3)_n$	50.60	51.63	2.43	2.36	18.03	18.05
$(\text{Cs}_{2/3}\text{Zn}_{1/6}\text{PO}_3)_n$	50.00	49.64	6.20	6.10	17.26	17.36
$(\text{Cs}_{2/3}\text{Ni}_{1/6}\text{PO}_3)_n$	—	—	5.60	5.51	17.36	17.47

Analysis of the complex derivatives: All these derivatives have been analysed for cesium, phosphorous and the bivalent metals. Cesium was analysed by a Beckman DU Spectrophotometer with a cesium photo cell attachment. The metals were analysed by standard methods described by Vogel¹⁷. Phosphorous was estimated as ammonium phosphomolybdate by volumetric method. The results of the analyses are given in Table I.

Conductance data : The conductance of all these derivatives have been measured at different formal concentrations. The specific conductance at different formal concentrations is given in Table III and is plotted in fig. 1. The equivalent conductance is given in Table IV and is plotted against square root of concentration in fig. 2.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

17. A. I. Vogel, "Textbook of Quantitative Analysis", Longmans, Third Ed. (1961).

TABLE II

Number average molecular weights of complex cesium polymetaphosphate derivatives
 $[\text{Cs}_4\text{M}(\text{PO}_3)_6]_n-800^\circ$

Compound Mol. Weight	(CsPO ₃) _n 10000	M=Ca 5550	=Zn 8350	=Ni 5550	=Mg 3850
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Number average molecular weights: The number average molecular weights of all these derivatives have been determined with the help of endgroup titrations. In almost all the cases the pH of the solution was lowered to about 3 and then it was titrated with the help of standard alkali. The observed molecular weights are given in Table II.

DISCUSSION

The high molecular weights of all these derivatives obtained by endgroup titration method show that they are polymeric in nature.

From the conductance data the following conclusions may be drawn :

(a) The curves obtained by plotting Sp. conductance against formal concentration are similar in nature to those obtained for complex sodium polymetaphosphate¹², complex potassium polymetaphosphate¹⁴ and complex lithium polymetaphosphate¹⁶ derivatives. They are also similar in nature to those obtained for other synthetic polyelectrolytes.¹⁸

(b) The plot of equivalent conductance against square root of concentration gives curves with concave up shapes which is also characteristic of polyelectrolytes.

(c) The conductances of cesium polymetaphosphate and its complex derivatives are higher than those of sodium and lithium derivatives. This may be due to weaker counter ion binding and greater degree of dissociation for cesium in comparison to lithium and sodium¹⁹.

TABLE III

Specific conductance ($K \times 10^{-4}$) of complex cesium polymetaphosphate derivatives
 $[\text{Cs}_4\text{M}(\text{PO}_3)_6]_n$

ml of f/33.33 soln. diluted to 50 ml.	(Cs PO ₃) _n	M=Ca	= Zn	= Ni	= Mg
1	0.3512	0.4567	0.3796	0.4426	0.5301
2	0.6009	0.7902	0.6563	0.7969	0.9363
5	1.319	1.795	1.387	1.756	2.021
15	3.512	4.681	3.649	4.322	5.107
75	5.675	7.112	5.630	6.610	7.912
40	8.513	10.21	8.026	9.603	11.40

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19. U. P. Strauss and P. D. Ross, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 5295.

20. J. R. Van Wazer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 645.

TABLE IV

Equivalent conductance (λ) of complex cesium polymetaphosphates $[\text{Cs}_4\text{M}(\text{PO}_3)_6]_n$

$\sqrt{C} \times 10^2$	$(\text{CsPO}_3)_n$	M=Ca	Zn	Ni	Mg
2.45	58.52	76.12	63.25	73.72	88.35
3.46	50.07	65.85	54.69	66.40	78.00
5.48	43.96	59.83	46.23	58.53	67.36
9.48	39.02	52.00	40.54	48.01	56.74
12.22	37.84	47.42	37.53	44.07	52.74
15.49	35.46	43.54	33.44	40.00	47.49

The molecular weight data and the conductance studies show that these are polymeric compounds and have got similar nature to that of Graham's salt. As the Graham's salt has been assigned a long chain polymeric structure^{3,20}, the cesium polymetaphosphate may also be given a structure of the type :

and the complex derivatives may be given a structure :

Although the structures given here are still tentative but other studies like powder spectrum of these amorphous glasses by X-ray, NMR and IR studies may throw some light on the nature of these complex derivatives. Work in these directions, is in progress.

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